

CLASSROOM ASSESSMENT CYCLE AND LEARNERS' READING PARTICIPATION IN TAGUM NORTH DISTRICT

CRISCELLITA R. BONCALES

Abstract. The study unfolded the estimate of the classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation among the Elementary Schools of Tagum North District, Tagum City Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that classroom assessment cycle in terms of modifying instruction, learning targets, gathering evidence and assessment data is extensive, while, comprehension of senior high school learners in terms of discussing with friend, listening to the lesson, being relevant to the teaching and learning activities and writing is moderately extensive. There is a relationship between classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation. Domains of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets, gathering evidence analyzing assessment data and modifying instruction significantly influenced learners' reading participation. Future research may Conduct longitudinal studies to examine the long-term impact of the Classroom Assessment Cycle on learners' reading skills, motivation, and overall academic achievement. Investigate how sustained implementation of the cycle influences students' reading participation beyond the immediate instructional context.

KEY WORDS

1. classroom assessment 2. reading participation 3. assessment cycle

1. Introduction

Assessment is viewed as one of the vital pedagogical practices to both teaching and learning. It entails a sum of instruments and techniques which are used in classrooms and help teachers accurately define their learners needs and competencies. In other words, it is a pedagogical and instructive activity needed to gather information about learners so as to properly identify their strengths and weaknesses (Collins, et.al, 2022). Across the world, assessment offers opportunities for teachers to pinpoint teaching goals and to know the extent to which the expected goals are attained. Essentially, it renders the teaching-learning process more effective and reliable as teachers can adjust their instruction and link it to the assessment results and student's needs. In other words, assessment is an essential component of classroom instruction that is designed to detect students weaknesses and demands in any learning subject. Accordingly, teachers can make the right decisions and provide constructive feedback to their learners (reed, et.al., 2019). More importantly, classroom assessment should entail ef-

fective techniques and tools that vary according to the teaching subjects and grades. Certainly, it needs to relate to the previously offered courses because it should aim to maximize and enhance students skills and abilities. In the Philippines, assessment on reading comprehension among learners across private and public schools, are given to elementary learners who are taught language skills such as reading. Reading enables students to gain knowledge from printed materials like textbooks, newspaper, magazine, and others. To make reading class a success, the students need to participate actively. Therefore, what should be there is an effort to make students active to participate in the classroom especially on reading comprehension class (Stahl, et.al, 2022). Students' participation is usually defined as the activities or behaviors during the teaching learning process. The activity or behavior is connected with the learning activities such as reading the material, writing, listening to the teacher, asking questions, giving a comment, doing a task, and discussing with friends (Gunobgunob, 2020). The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Assessment Tool is aimed to be used as a classroom-based assessment tool to measure and describe students' reading performance. Information gathered from the assessment can help classroom teachers design and provide appropriate reading instruction for their students. The Informal Reading Inventory (IRI) is an individually-administered diagnostic tool that assesses a student's reading comprehension and reading accuracy. On its deeper sense, PHIL IRI is an assessment tool that evaluates the reading proficiency of the elementary school pupils on various levels. It is the first validated instrument that intends to measure the pupils' reading comprehension level. However, until the current school year, schools are still taking more time to seek effective strategies that can make reading comprehension explicitly evident on learners' performance. The DepED Regional Office XI and the rest of the Schools Division find results very low in terms of learners' reading comprehension. A lot of data and information can be traced showing evidence that learners' reading level and comprehension performance are way down low and poor given several activities and interventions strategies. In the Elementary Schools of Tagum North District, School Heads, Teachers and Parents and other stakeholders are always in collaboration as to augmenting the reading comprehension performance of learners. It is on the purpose of the researcher to to take some investigations on the angle of exploring the determinants of assessment of reading comprehension in the classroom setting, a much deductive way to measure and discover learners' participation as well to each teaching and learning processes, especially so in the newer sensibilities of full face to face classroom interaction. Thus, this study is presented.

2. Methodology

This proposed research sets the method that introduces the details on how the study was conducted. Method of the research presented the research design, where its applications in the context of the study were clear and doable; research respondents in its selection and sampling method given a population and scope of the study; the research instrument in gathering data; the data collection procedure and its emphasis to ethics and health protocol; and lastly, the data analysis technique are all discussed to shed clear directions of the respective process.

2.1. Research Design—This study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. A correlational research design investigates relationships between

variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. A correlation reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. (Pallant, 2020). Findings from correlational research can be used to determine prevalence and relationships among variables, and to forecast events from current data and knowledge. In spite of its many uses, prudence is required when using the methodology and analysing data. On the other hand, this type of research tries to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities in order to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). In this study, indicators under independent variable such as determining learning targets, gathering performance evidences, analyzing assessment data and modifying instructions are used to estimate the extent of classroom assessment cycle in reading comprehension (Habib, 2016) among teachers are assumed to be associated with dependent variable, learners' participation, where its indicators are discussing with friend, listening to the lesson, being relevant to the teaching and learning activities and writing in Tagum North District, Tagum City. Using the design mentioned, it is assumed that variables along with its indicators mentioned, the researcher empirically provide evidence that presented hypothesis shall be null and void in nature.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Teachers of Tagum North District, Tagum City Division. She used Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective school within the mentioned District. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and

its contribution to their professional development status. As much as possible, these teacher-respondents are teaching three years and above in the public school service in the respective schools to measure their competence in responding to the queries of the study and how they performed and contributed to the betterment of the school's reading profile using the Phil IRI and the learners' participation on the classroom assessment cycle in reading comprehension given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Further, these teacher-respondents are expected to have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings including SLAC sessions on the pedagogies in integrating reading program in the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from Habib (2016) and Iskander and Husin (2022). The researcher took time in gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content and that supports the instrument, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of measuring the extent teachers' classroom assessment cycle on reading comprehension in terms of learning targets, gathering evidences, analyzing data, and modifying instructions. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of learners' participation in terms of discussing with friend, listening to the lesson, being relevant to the teaching and learning activities and writing. Contents of the statements of the survey were placed in the contexts based on the definition of the variables. Further,

the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.917 which means that 91.7 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant 2010).

Scale Descriptive Rating Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The classroom assessment cycle is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The classroom assessment cycle is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The classroom assessment cycle is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The classroom assessment cycle is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The classroom assessment cycle is not manifested

Scale Descriptive Rating Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The learners’ reading participation is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The learners’ reading participation is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learners’ reading participation is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learners’ reading participation is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learners’ reading participation is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements steps explain the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data most especially in the current full face to face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. On the second week of February 2023, the researcher started to conceptualize the contents and objective of the thesis proposal. She then, prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study

underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004), and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the schools of Matina District Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process which were sent to the randomly selected

respondents via email addresses, and for respondents who do not have access to internet. Likewise a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets were given to each of them. Once done, link was sent, and right away responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed in data gathering which commenced on the third week of March 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Results of the

preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of March 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime on the fourth week of April 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of March 2023.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of classroom assessment cycle, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of learners' reading participation in Tagum North District, Tagum City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between the classroom assessment cycle and the learners' reading participation in Tagum

North District, Tagum City. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the domains of classroom assessment cycle significantly influence learners' learners' reading participation in Tagum North District, Tagum City (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Classroom Assessment Cycle Assessment is seen as the practice of detecting and defining the students knowledge, understandings, abilities, and skills. It is a classroom activity used to stimulate learning by collecting data and offering constructive feedback (Black William, 1998) as cited by Habib (2016). In other words, assessment is the process of knowing about how students are progressing in their learning to make the right decision in designing and planning classroom instruction. Definitely, collecting data about students, analysing evidence, and refining instruction are assessment stages by which teachers can increase the learning out-

comes. This classroom assessment cycle shapes the classroom assessment procedure which focuses on enhancing students performance. It denotes that assessment comprises four key steps: clarifying the learning objectives, gathering information in a variety of ways, scrutinizing assessment data, and adjusting instruction. Indeed, teachers should use the evidence to monitor progress, increase performance, and improve instruction. Besides, assessment involves the process of evaluating, marking, and grading students performance. It is viewed as a method of collecting, synthesizing, and interpreting information in order to diagnose students prob-

lems, to judge their academic performance, to plan classroom instruction, and to respond to students needs (Airasian, 1994) Habib (2016) stated. In brief, assessment is defined as being diagnostic, formative, and summative. These three components are used together to help both teachers and learners determine what should be done to enhance the teaching input and the learning outcomes.

Table 1 shows the extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Determines what behavior should be looking for as students demonstrate their level of knowl-

edge and skill (4.10), Aligns learning objectives with instructional strategies and assessments to ensure that everyone involved is aware of the expectations (4.00) and Energizes and motivate students to become actively engaged in and committed to the learning process (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, Describes what students will learn and be able to do by the end of a class, unit, project, or even a course (3.30) and Leads to more targeted instruction and successful learning experiences for students (3.10) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.58 denotes extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 1. Extent of Classroom Assessment Cycle in Terms of Learning Targets

No	Learning Targets	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Determines what behavior should be looking for as students demonstrate their level of knowledge and skill	4.10	Extensive
2	Describes what students will learn and be able to do by the end of a class, unit, project, or even a course	3.30	Moderately Extensive
3	Aligns learning objectives with instructional strategies and assessments to ensure that everyone involved is aware of the expectations	4.00	Extensive
4	Energizes and motivate students to become actively engaged in and committed to the learning process	3.40	Extensive
5	Leads to more targeted instruction and successful learning experiences for students	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.58	Extensive

Learning targets are concrete goals written in student-friendly language that clearly describe what students will learn and be able to do by the end of a class, unit, project, or even a course. Learning objectives set student expectations, guide their learning processes, and help them focus their study time for the upcoming exam(s).

Although many teachers create courses without ever articulating exactly what they want students to take away from the experience, most well designed courses begin with specific goals and student-learning objectives. Learning objectives communicate instructional expectations to students and direct the design

of teaching. Goals and objectives are similar in that they describe the intended purposes and expected results of teaching activities and establish the foundation for assessment (Nel, 2021). The most effective teaching and the most meaningful student learning happen when teachers design the right learning targets for today's lesson and use it along with their students to aim for and assess understanding. A shared learning target is not just simply relaying the teaching objective to the students by writing it up on the board and/or telling students what the objective is in a sentence or two. Instead, when sharing learning targets with students the teacher is making sure that students comprehend what those objectives mean, as well as the criteria for mastering the objectives and how to get there. Rather than just having students repeat the objective, students should be able to understand the learning target and know what exemplary work looks like (Yilmaz, 2022). Further, Using the adapted version of the Elementary Reading Attitudes Survey by McKenna and Kear, 177 Grades 5-6 pupils in Bamban, Tarlac were surveyed to determine their attitudes toward reading. The survey confirmed the hypothesis that gender is indeed a determinant of the pupils' attitudes toward reading. While girls were found to have more positive attitudes toward reading, it was also found that as age increases, positive reading attitudes decline. This poses a challenge to educators in providing opportunities through setting clear learning targets to develop more permanent positive attitudes toward reading as a lifelong habit (Gunobgunob-Mirasol, 2020). Konrad (2014) claimed that Teachers must unpack these standards and develop explicit learning targets to make these rigorous standards accessible to their students. This task

In some ways, techniques that could be used to gather testimonial evidence include: interviews, focus groups, surveys, expert opinions,

can be especially challenging for special educators who must balance standards-based education with individualized instruction. Their paper describes the value of clarifying learning targets, defines different types of targets, and provides strategies and resources to assist practitioners in unpacking standards to develop learning targets. In addition, the authors suggest how the standards can be used to drive individualized education program planning to maximize learning for students with disabilities and increase the likelihood of student success.

Table 2 shows the extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of gathering evidence. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Makes informed and consistent judgements to improve student learning (4.15) and Backs up or refute arguments, and it helps us to make decisions at work (3.50) re oftentimes manifested; while, Increases likelihood of positive child or student outcomes (3.35), Allows us to work out what is effective and what is not (3.30) and Provides reliable basis for identifying progress (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.50 denotes extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of gathering evidence is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Direct evidence measures student learning by examining student work or performance directly. It can offer insight into what and to what degree students have learned through evaluating exams, papers, performances, observations, or other artifacts of student work. Evidence is used to back up or refute arguments, and it helps us to make decisions at work. Using evidence allows us to work out what is effective and what is not (Yilmaz and Melekoglu, 2022).

and external confirmation. Documentary evidence is obtained from information and data found in documents or databases. Assessment

Table 2. Extent of Classroom Assessment Cycle in Terms of Gathering Results

No	Gathering Results	Mean
1	Backs up or refute arguments, and it helps us to make decisions at work	3.50
2	Allows us to work out what is effective and what is not	3.30
3	Increases likelihood of positive child or student outcomes	3.35
4	Makes informed and consistent judgments to improve student learning	4.15
5	Provides reliable basis for identifying progress	3.20
Overall Mean		3.50

for Learning is one of a process of gathering information about students' knowledge, skills and understanding in order to inform teaching. It can be used as an ongoing part of the curriculum or it may take place at key stages such as end-of-year exams. Benefits in gathering learning evidences could increased likelihood of positive child or student outcomes. Increased accountability because there are data to back up the selection of a practice or program, which in turn facilitates support from administrators, parents, and others (Collins, et.al., 2021). The reading program assessment process involves gathering evidence of student learning. All reading programs are required to collect direct evidence of student learning for each program learning outcome. However, the evidence gathered can vary across programs and depend on each program's learning outcomes and the opportunities in each curriculum map to collect data (Stahl, et.al., 2022). Direct evidence measures student learning by examining student work or performance directly. It can further offer insight into what and to what degree students have learned through evaluating exams, papers, performance, observations, or other artifacts or student work. Direct evidence is compelling in that it offers the ability to make judgements about the relative degree of learning or mastery that students have achieved. Examples of direct evidence are evaluation of capstone projects, evaluation of student portfolio, performance valuation, comprehensive examinations, performance

in proficiency exams. It is important that direct measures validity measure the specific learning outcomes in question and provide useful information (Konrad, et.al., 2014). Moreover, supporting evidence is not evidence of learning per se, but has a role in the assessment for student learning. It can help illustrate a program's successes or needs, provide context for interpreting assessment data, or aid in designing assessments plans that address pressing questions of interest to the program (Bell, et.al., 2022). Bell and Wheldall (2022) conducted to explore how the relationships between reading comprehension constructs change according to word reading accuracy, as measured in a large convenience sample of school-aged students (Years 3-6) with reading difficulties. Multiple regression analyses containing interaction variables were conducted, to determine whether word reading accuracy moderated the relationships between the dependent variable (i.e. reading comprehension) and independent variables (i.e. each of vocabulary and nonword reading accuracy). Samosa, et.al., (2021) intended on the development of the learners' reading comprehension and story analysis skills under the implementation of PowToon as an innovative instructional material for learners' development in reading comprehension and story analysis skills. This study provided various evidence on how innovation can be a great step in developing the learners reading comprehension and story analysis skills. The data that this study generated in

terms of the success it shown over the development of the learners were significant in terms of their level of reading and analysis skills. Furthermore the information gained from this study will benefit English teachers by yielding information about the effectiveness of using Pow-Toon as an innovative instructional material to develop learners' reading and analyzing skills.

Table 3 shows the extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of analyzing assessment data. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Makes clear, trace the development, and give reasons for and identify the most important aspects, challenges or points regarding the particular topic (4.35) is always manifested; Assesses the strengths and weaknesses

Analyzing data includes determining how to organize, synthesize, interrelate, compare, and present the assessment results. These decisions are guided by what assessment questions are asked, the types of data that are available, as well as the needs and wants of the audience/stakeholders. Methodical analysis of assessment data provides the evidence a practitioner needs to improve teaching and learning for the group and individuals within it. Data analysis includes how it is organize, synthesize, compare, and present the assessment data. Data analysis helps teachers understand their students' learning abilities and challenges, and facilitates an ingrained cultural process that uses detailed inputs (information) to ensure optimal outputs (results for students). Starting with a clear objective is an essential step in the data analysis process. By recognizing the business problem that you want to solve and setting well-defined goals, it'll be way easier to decide on the data you need (van der Kleij, et.al., 2023). To give meaning to the information that has been collected, it needs to be analyzed for context, understanding, and to draw conclusions. This step gives

of the particular topic and give reasons for assessment (4.00) is oftentimes manifested, while, Provides a means to look at student performance to offer evidence about student learning in the curriculum, provide information about program strengths and weaknesses, and guide decision-making (3.25) and Helps teachers understand students' learning abilities and challenges, and facilitates an ingrained cultural process that uses detailed inputs to ensure optimal outputs (3.20) are sometimes manifested, and lastly, Decides which needs have the highest priority (2.15) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.50 denotes extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of analyzing assessment data is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

the information meaning; it is essential to effectively communicate and utilize the assessment results. Teachers use the data to assess a student's performance, strengths, weaknesses, and progress. Additional information on an individual student's background allows the teacher to diagnose possible causes of poor performance and apply remedies. Administrators and teachers may study standardized test scores, attendance data, and behavior data to make decisions for their schools. Processes like these can catch students falling through the cracks, identify gaps in curriculum coverage, and better align curriculums across departments and grades (Seipel, et.al., 2013).

Table 4 shows the extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of modifying instruction. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Keep standards of learning the same while changing the learning approach and modifications change the level of instruction (4.35) and Removes barriers to learning and allows all students to demonstrate mastery (4.20) are always manifested; while, Ensure students have

Table 3. Extent of Classroom Assessment Cycle in Terms of Analyzing Assessment Data

No	Analyzing Assessment Data	Mean
1	Provides a means to look at student performance to offer evidence about student learning in the curriculum, provide information about program strengths and weaknesses, and guide decision-making	3.25
2	Assesses the strengths and weaknesses of the particular topic and give reasons for assessment	4.00
3	Makes clear, trace the development, and give reasons for and identify the most important aspects, challenges or points regarding the particular topic.	4.35
4	Decides which needs have the highest priority	2.15
5	Helps teachers understand students' learning abilities and challenges, and facilitates an ingrained cultural process that uses detailed inputs to ensure optimal outputs	3.20
Overall Mean		3.39
		Extensive

the necessary foundation for learning (3.40) is oftentimes manifested, and, Ensures that the content is adapted at the level of the individual learner within the institution (3.20) and Change the way that material is presented or the way that students respond to show their learning (3.15) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.66 denotes extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of modifying instruction is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 4. Extent of Classroom Assessment Cycle in Terms of Modifying Instruction

No	Modifying Instruction	Mean
1	Ensure students have the necessary foundation for learning	3.40
2	Removes barriers to learning and allows all students to demonstrate mastery	4.20
3	Keep standards of learning the same while changing the learning approach and modifications change the level of instruction	4.35
4	Change the way that material is presented or the way that students respond to show their learning	3.15
5	Ensures that the content is adapted at the level of the individual learner within the institution	3.20
Overall Mean		3.66
		Extensive

An academic modification is a change to what a student is taught or expected to do in school. An example of a modification is less homework or easier assignments. Before using a modification, it's often better to try changing how a child learns, or try using a different teaching strategy. However, instructional strategies can be modified to ensure that students have the necessary foundation for learning. For example, before encountering new concepts or vocabulary, students can be immersed in discussion and examples to build a necessary referential base for deeper learning (Samosa, et.al., 2021). If a student cannot achieve success at the targeted level, using modifications

to make the material more manageable for the student is an important part of teaching. Modifications allow students to learn at their present level rather than failing to comprehend information above their understanding. Decades of research offer important understandings about the nature of comprehension and its development. Drawing on both classic and contemporary research, Duke, et.al., (2021) identified some key understandings about reading comprehension processes and instruction, including these: Comprehension instruction should begin early, teaching word-reading and bridging skills (including graphophonological semantic cognitive flexibility, morphological awareness, and reading

fluency) supports reading comprehension development, reading comprehension is not automatic even when fluency is strong, teaching text structures and features fosters reading comprehension development, comprehension processes vary by what and why we are reading, comprehension strategy instruction improves comprehension, vocabulary and knowledge building support reading comprehension development, supporting engagement with text (volume reading, discussion and analysis of text, and writing) fosters comprehension development, and instructional practices that kindle reading motivation improve comprehension. Moreover, Li, Gan, Leung, and An (2022) investigated the effect of explicit reading strategy instruction on reading comprehension, reading strategy use, reading motivation, and reading self-efficacy in Chinese university EFL learners. The data were collected through five major instruments: a reading comprehension test, a reading strategy questionnaire, a reading motivation questionnaire, a reading self-efficacy questionnaire, and a semi-structured interview. Independent-samples t-test results showed that there was a significant difference in reading comprehension between the experimental group and the control group

after the reading strategy instruction, suggesting that students who received reading strategy instruction made significant improvement in their reading comprehension. ANCOVA analysis of pre- and post-questionnaires results showed that there were no significant changes in reading strategy use, reading motivation, and reading self-efficacy at the end of the strategy instruction. Furthermore, interview data, showed that experimental group students held very positive attitudes toward the reading strategy training. Interview results further suggested that lack of significant changes in strategy use, motivation, and self-efficacy at the end of strategy training could be explained by a dynamic interplay of individual and contextual factors.

Table 5 shows the summary of the extent of classroom assessment cycle. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: modifying instruction (3.66), learning targets (3.58), and gathering evidence (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while, analyzing assessment data (3.39) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.53 denotes the extent of extent of classroom assessment cycle is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 5. Summary on the Classroom Assessment Cycle

No	Classroom Assessment Cycle	Mean
1	Learning Targets	3.58
2	Gathering Evidence	3.50
3	Analyzing Assessment Data	3.39
4	Modifying Instruction	3.66
Overall Mean		3.53
Extensive		

Learning targets are explicit statements that describe the intended learning outcomes for students. They provide a roadmap for both teachers and students, outlining the knowledge, skills, and understanding that students should acquire

during a specific instructional period. Well-defined learning targets align with curriculum standards and reflect the desired educational objectives. They act as a guide for planning instruction and serve as a reference point for

assessing student progress. The second component of the Classroom Assessment Cycle involves gathering evidence of student learning. This step involves utilizing a variety of assessment methods and tools to collect data on student performance. These assessments can take various forms, such as tests, quizzes, projects, observations, and portfolios. By employing multiple assessment methods, teachers can obtain a comprehensive understanding of students' strengths, areas for improvement, and individual learning styles. Gathering evidence should be an ongoing process that occurs throughout instruction to provide timely feedback and guide instructional decisions. Once evidence of student learning has been collected, the next step is to analyze the assessment data. Analysis involves interpreting the information gathered from assessments to gain insights into student achievement and progress towards the learning targets. Teachers examine the data to identify patterns, trends, and areas of concern. This analysis helps to identify individual student needs, identify instructional gaps, and inform the effectiveness of instructional strategies. Analyzing assessment data provides a deeper understanding of student learning, enabling teachers to make informed instructional decisions. The final component of the Classroom Assessment Cycle involves modifying instruction based on the analysis of assessment data. This step is crucial for adapting teaching strategies and interventions to meet students' diverse learning needs. Based on the insights gained from analyzing assessment data, teachers can adjust their instructional methods, differentiate instruction, provide additional support, or offer enrichment opportunities. Modifying instruction ensures that teaching aligns with students' current levels of understanding, promotes growth, and maximizes their learning potential. It is an iterative process that responds to the evolving needs of the students. The components of the Classroom Assessment Cycle are interconnected and in-

terdependent. Clear learning targets provide a framework for gathering evidence, as assessments are designed to measure student progress towards those targets. The evidence collected informs the analysis of assessment data, enabling teachers to identify areas of strength and weakness. This analysis, in turn, informs instructional decision-making, leading to modifications in teaching strategies and approaches. The cycle continues as modifications in instruction generate new evidence, which feeds into the ongoing analysis and adaptation of instructional practices.

Learners' Reading Participation Reading comprehension is a vital aspect of education, and it is an essential skill that is developed in senior high school learners. In recent years, researchers have focused on investigating the factors that affect reading comprehension and how to improve it. Active participation is the consistent engagement of the minds of all students with that which is to be learned. The following strategies must utilize the key attribute that every student must show their signal, card, slate, etc. at the same time. These methods might include things like lectures, discussions, and small-group work. If you are teaching a lecture course, set aside time during each lecture to ask and answer questions, to ask students to solve a problem, or to discuss an issue. Students are only going to listen to an instructor speak for about 10 to 15 minutes. Breaking up lectures with activities, interactive questions, and other ways to keep the students engaged will not only increase classroom participation but also keep them focused. Understanding learner participation is essential to any learning environment to enhance teaching and learning, especially in large scale digital spaces, such as massive open online courses. However, there is a lack of research to fully capture the dynamic nature of massive open online courses and the different ways learners participate in these emerging massive e-learning ecologies. To fill in the research

gap, Haniya ang Paqutte (2020) attempted to investigate the relationship between how learners choose to participate in a massive open online course, their initial motivation for learning, and the barriers they faced throughout the course. Reported similar motivations and barriers, but described differences in how their participation was impacted by those factors. These findings are significant to gain insights about learners' needs which in turn serve as the basis to innovate more adaptive and personalized learning experiences and thus advance learning in these large scale environments.

Table 6 shows the extent of learners' reading participation in terms of discussing with friend. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Keeps eyes and ears open (4.10), and Listens actively (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while, Talks slowly (3.25) is sometimes manifested, and Pays attention to details (2.50) and Uses right words (2.40) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.15 denotes extent of extent of learners' reading participation in terms of discussing with friend is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 6. Extent of Learners' Reading Participation in Terms of Discussing with Friend

No	Discussing with Friend	Mean
1	Listens actively	3.50
2	Pays attention to details	2.50
3	Keeps eyes and ears open	4.10
4	Talks slowly	3.25
5	Uses right words	2.40
Overall Mean		3.15
		Moderately Extensive

Discussion is important to learning in all disciplines because it helps students process information rather than simply receive it. Leading a discussion requires skills different from lecturing. The goal of a discussion is to get students to practice thinking about the course material. Discussion methods are a variety of forums for open-ended, collaborative exchange of ideas among a teacher and students or among students for the purpose of furthering students thinking, learning, problem solving, understanding, or literary appreciation. Classroom discussion is a practice in which the instructor and students share views on a specific topic previously lectured. Promoting and facilitating class-

room discussions can not only help students learn from one another but also help students understand and retain the lecture better. Belonging promotes positive mental health, physical wellbeing and a better focus on learning. It can also give us a sense of purpose and meaning. Friendships with other students can give children a sense of belonging and a greater connection to their school. More students learn more material when they work together, cooperatively, talking through the material with each other and making sure that all group members understand, than when students compete with one another or work alone, individualistically (Buphate, et.al., 2022). Hamzah , et.al., (2022)

aimed to explore motivation factors that contribute to learning among young adult learners in selected schools in Kuala Selangor, Malaysia. Four focus group discussions had been conducted to collect the data via a semi-structured interview. The themes that emerged from the analysis are reasons for coming to school, interest in schooling, disinterest in schooling, subjects of interest, effort to increase academic performance and factors contributing to academic achievement. The findings show that although teachers and friends can be motivating factors that encouraged the learners to go to school, these factors were also hindrances influenced success or failure. Being young adult learners, their cognitive level is still developing and they are influenced by physiological changes. Hence, educators and policy makers need to ensure that

young adult learners, especially those who are at risk of dropping out of school, are motivated to complete their secondary education.

Table 7 shows the extent of learners' reading participation in terms of listening to the lesson. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Paying close attention (3.50), Asks and gives feedback (3.45) and Avoids distractions (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, Shows interest with questions (3.15) is sometimes manifested, and Paraphrases on what has been said (2.20) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.14 denotes extent of learners' reading participation in terms of listening to the lesson is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 7. Extent of Learners' Reading Participation in Terms of Listening To The Lesson

No	Listening to the Lesson	Mean
1	Paying close attention	3.50
2	Asks and gives feedback	3.45
3	Paraphrases on what has been said	2.20
4	Shows interest with questions	3.15
5	Avoids distractions	3.40
Overall Mean: Moderately Extensive		3.14

Listening is giving attention to a sound or action. When listening, a person hears what others are saying and tries to understand what it means. The act of listening involves complex affective, cognitive and behavioral processes. Listening enhance ability to understand better and make a better communicator, it also makes the experience of speaking to you more enjoyable to other people. Teachers allow students to follow directions, understand expectations, and make sense of oral communication. As children improve as listeners, they learn to use the same strategies to improve their command of

the other language arts. Listening is vital in the language classroom because it provides input for the learner. Without understanding input at the right level, any learning simply cannot begin. they hear is an impetus, not an obstacle, to interaction and learning. Listening is often a challenge for foreign/second language learners. Unlike other language skills, listening requires immediate understanding and processing (Vandergrift, 2004) and background knowledge of the target language culture (Vandergrift, 2007; Walker, 2014). Krashen (1985) argued that language can be acquired with comprehen-

sible input; therefore, studies have focused on developing listening skills through both intensive and extensive listening (e.g., Chang Read, 2006; Jones, 2008; Renandya, 2011). Elmetaher (2021) have taken a different approach in that developing listening skills might happen through interaction where learners discuss and negotiate, and not solely through intensive input (Ellis, 1997).

Table 8 shows the extent of learners’ reading participation in terms of being relevant to the teaching and learning activities. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Connects learn-

ing with the real world (3.40) is oftentimes manifested, while, Engages in study materials with friends (3.30), Participates in the class and collaborate with others (3.25), and Develop skills such as decision making and problem solving, team work, and presentation skills (3.15) are sometimes manifested, and Increases drive for exploration and discovery (2.10) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.04 denotes extent of learners’ reading participation in terms of being relevant to the teaching and learning activities is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 8. Extent of Learners’ Reading Participation in Terms of Being Relevant to the Teaching and Learning Activities

No	Being Relevant to the Teaching and Learning Activities	Mean
1	Engages in study materials with friends	3.30
2	Participates in the class and collaborate with others	3.25
3	Increases drive for exploration and discovery	2.10
4	Develop skills such as decision making and problem solving, team work, and presentation skills	3.15
5	Connects learning with the real world	3.40
Overall Mean: Moderately Extensive		3.04

A learning and teaching activity enables students to engage with a facilitator to learn the knowledge or skills required to achieve the desired educational outcome. Some of the best ways to make learning “stick” include connecting content with meaning, encouraging self-testing instead of rote memorization, and giving frequent, low-stakes assessments. Involvement in play stimulates a child’s drive for exploration and discovery. This motivates the child to gain mastery over their environment, promot-

ing focus and concentration. It also enables the child to engage in the flexible and higher-level thinking processes deemed essential for the 21st century learner (Asogwa, et.al., 2022). Dogan and Batdi (2021) claimed that an increase in research on the teaching of creativity in learning environments is being witnessed as more studies continue to reveal its effects on learning outcomes and academic achievement. Thus, any investigative attempt to examine the relevant approaches to teaching of creative thinking skills

is appreciated within the creativity literature. However, it is evident that the research on brainstorming as a creativity-promoting technique within an educational context has been overlooked for a while. Therefore, this research synthesis tried to recombine and reinterpret the results of some qualitative studies on the impacts of brainstorming technique on learners' achievement. Learners have their dominant intelligence which gave rise to the different learning styles, a dominant mode of information reception, processing, and storage. Asogwa, et.al., (2022) determined the extent each learner group perceives the use of Facebook for learning as useful and easy to use. Findings from the study showed that there were more visual learners among the study sample than other learner groups.

ing participation in terms of writing. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Presents focus, development, unity, coherence, and correctness (3.25), Express feelings, explore an idea, evaluate, mediate, problem solve, or argue for or against an idea (3.20) and Shows fluency, content, conventions, syntax, and vocabulary (3.10) sometimes manifested; while, Evaluates the idea and information the author has presented (2.30) and Follows the impulses of their own mind, allowing thoughts and inspiration to appear to them without premeditation (2.15) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.80 denotes extent of learners' reading participation in terms of writing is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 9 shows the extent of learners' read-

Table 9. Extent of Learners' Reading Participation in Terms of Writing

No	Writing	Mean
1	Shows fluency, content, conventions, syntax, and vocabulary	3.10
2	Presents focus, development, unity, coherence, and correctness	3.25
3	Evaluates the idea and information the author has presented	2.30
4	Follows the impulses of their own mind, allowing thoughts and inspiration to appear to them without premeditation	2.15
5	Express feelings, explore an idea, evaluate, mediate, problem solve, or argue for or against an idea	3.20
Overall Mean: Moderately Extensive		2.80

Basic writing skills are sometimes called the "mechanics" of writing. Skills like research, planning and outlining, editing, revising, spelling and grammar, and organization are critical components of the writing process. In the workplace, writing skills examples include, doc-

umenting a process for someone else to learn it. When the learner write, he/she get to understand more about the rules of grammar and language syntax. As such, better able to organize thoughts, ideas, and information sensibly and coherently. Likewise, spelling ability, knowl-

edge of words, and use of punctuation get better when develop content regularly (Madarbakus-Ring, 2020). Writing expresses who we are as people. Writing makes our thinking and learning visible and permanent. Writing fosters our ability to explain and refine our ideas to others and ourselves. While having a grasp on proper grammar, spelling, and punctuation won't make you a good writer, these basics are more essential to academic and professional writing than most other genres (although advertising is often a curious hybrid of creative and non-fiction writing). However, there are certain qualities that most examples of good writing share. The following is a brief description of five qualities of good writing: focus, development, unity, coherence, and correctness. The qualities described here are especially important for academic and expository writing. Writing might be beneficial to cognitive skills because it requires focusing of attention, planning and forethought, organization of one's thinking, and reflective thought, among other abilities, thereby sharpening these

skills through practice and reinforcement (Dogan and Batdi, 2021).

Table 10 shows the summary of the extent of comprehension of senior high school learners. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: discussing with friend (3.15), listening to the lesson (3.14), being relevant to the teaching and learning activities (3.04) and writing (2.80) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes that extent of comprehension of senior high school learners is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. One crucial component of reading participation is engaging in discussions with friends or peers. Collaborative discussions provide learners with opportunities to exchange ideas, share interpretations, and construct meaning collectively. When learners discuss their reading materials with others, they are exposed to diverse perspectives and insights, fostering deeper comprehension and critical thinking.

Table 10. Summary of The Extent of Learners' Participation

No	Learners' Participation	Mean
1	discussing with friend	3.15
2	listening to the lesson	3.14
3	being relevant to the teaching and learning activities	3.04
4	writing	2.80
Overall Mean: Moderately Extensive		3.03

Additionally, discussing with friends promotes social interaction and enhances communication skills, allowing learners to articulate their thoughts, ask questions, and engage in meaningful dialogue about the text. Active listening during reading lessons plays a vital role in learners' reading participation. By attentively listening to the teacher's explanations, instructions, and discussions about reading materials,

learners can gain valuable insights, develop a deeper understanding of the text, and expand their vocabulary. Active listening also helps learners internalize the information being conveyed, making connections between their prior knowledge and new concepts presented during the lesson. Moreover, listening to the lesson cultivates important listening comprehension skills, such as identifying main ideas, recogniz-

ing supporting details, and making inferences, which are crucial for effective reading comprehension. To actively participate in reading, learners must engage with teaching and learning activities that are relevant to the text. This involves completing reading assignments, participating in guided reading activities, and actively responding to comprehension questions or prompts. By actively participating in these activities, learners are actively applying reading strategies, analyzing the text, and developing their reading skills. Being relevant to teaching and learning activities ensures that learners are actively involved in the reading process, rather than passively consuming information. Writing is a powerful tool for enhancing learners' reading participation. Through writing, learners are given the opportunity to synthesize their understanding of the text, organize their thoughts, and express their ideas in a coherent manner. Writing responses to reading prompts, summaries, reflections, or even creative writing activities based on the text help learners develop higher-order thinking skills, such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Writing also reinforces vocabulary acquisition, grammar usage, and sentence structure, all of which contribute to improved reading proficiency. Additionally, written responses provide teachers with valuable insights into learners' comprehension, allowing for targeted feedback and instructional support. Learn-

ers' reading participation is crucial for fostering comprehension, critical thinking, and overall reading proficiency. Engaging in discussions with friends promotes collaborative learning and the exchange of diverse perspectives. Active listening during lessons enables learners to gain insights, develop understanding, and improve listening comprehension skills. Being relevant to teaching and learning activities ensures learners actively engage with reading materials. Writing facilitates the synthesis and expression of ideas, reinforcing reading skills and promoting higher-order thinking. By actively participating in these aspects of reading, learners can become more effective readers and lifelong learners. Significant Relationship between Classroom Assessment Cycle and Learners' Reading Participation

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between classroom assessment cycle ($r=0.857$; $p_i.000$) and learners' reading participation. Table 11 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation, must be rejected for it provided an empirical evidence to show its correlation.

Table 11. Significant Relationship between Classroom Assessment Cycle and Learners' Reading Participation

Variables	Classroom Assessment Cycle	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Learners' Reading Participation	0.857	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

*significant @ $p_i0.05$.

Caroline Gipps (1994) who is often credited with introducing the term to the wider educational community, on the basis of making a clear distinction between assessment of learning, which is about evaluating what has been learnt and assessment for learning which is about using evaluation. Classroom assessment information should be the basis for important classroom processes and outcomes, students study and work patterns, students understanding of what they are learning, and teachers instructional and grading decisions. The validity of an assessment is how accurately the assessment measures the relevant performance of students. The primary focus of validity is whether the assessment measures what it is intended to measure, this will include if the assessment is appropriate for the criteria, the students and the education level. If a particular assessment were totally reliable, assessors acting independently using the same criteria and mark scheme would come to exactly the same judgement about a given piece of work. In the context of assessment on reading comprehension, assessment of reading proficiency is important as a way to understand students' overall reading abilities (based on some assumed construct of reading) and to determine if students are appropriately prepared for further learning and educational advancement. As for the assessment of reading comprehension, it involves several methods and procedures that are intended to display how adequately learners are able to read, comprehend, interpret, and analyze different types of texts. The most common reading comprehension assessment involves asking a child to

The Classroom Assessment Cycle is a systematic approach that promotes effective teaching and learning by informing instructional decisions and supporting student growth. This essay explores the significant influence of the Classroom Assessment Cycle on learners' read-

read a passage of text that is leveled appropriately for the child, and then asking some explicit, detailed questions about the content of the text. In addition, the theory of active learning by John Dewey (1899) who insisted that the old model of schooling is that students sitting in rows, memorizing and reciting, was antiquated. He said that students should be active, not passive and active learning. Dewey believed that human beings learn through a 'hands-on' approach. Later, Dewey (1966) uses the term active learner, stressing that learning is an active process in which learners construct their own meaning. In other words, learning is not a passive acceptance of presented knowledge by teachers, but is constructing meaning.

Domains of Classroom Assessment Cycle Significantly Influence Learners' Reading Participation

Table 12 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on domains of classroom assessment cycle significantly influence learners' reading participation. Domains of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets (0.001), gathering evidence (0.002), analyzing assessment data (0.000) and modifying instruction (0.001) significantly influence comprehension among senior high school learners. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.886 suggests that the domains of classroom assessment cycle, is explained by 88.6%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (264.588) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of learners' reading participation.

ing participation. By integrating assessment practices throughout the reading process, teachers can enhance students' engagement, comprehension, and overall reading participation. The Classroom Assessment Cycle begins with setting clear learning targets, which outline the

Table 12. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Classroom Assessment Cycle Significantly Influence Learners' Reading Participation

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decision
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001
H	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270
	LT	0.807	0.107	0.102	1.010
0.315	0.001	*Reject H0			
	GE	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299
0.196	0.002	*Reject H0			
	AAD	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098
0.038	0.000	*Reject H0			
	MI	0.683	0.086	0.499	5.654
0.001	0.001	*Reject H0			
R ²	= 0.886				
F-value	= 264.588				
p-value	= <0.001				
*Significant @ p<0.05					
LT- learning targets					
GE - gathering evidence					
AAD - analyzing assessment data					
MI - modifying instruction					

specific reading skills and outcomes students are expected to achieve. When teachers establish explicit learning targets related to reading, students have a clear understanding of what is expected of them. This clarity provides a sense of purpose and direction, motivating learners to actively engage in the reading process. By knowing the intended learning outcomes, students are more likely to participate actively and take ownership of their reading experiences. As part of the Classroom Assessment Cycle, teachers gather evidence of students' reading performance using various assessment methods. This evidence may include reading assessments, observations, and reading logs or journals. By collecting data on students' reading abilities and progress, teachers gain valuable insights into individual strengths, areas for improvement, and specific needs. This information allows teachers to tailor their instruction to meet the unique requirements of each learner, thereby fostering increased reading participation. The Classroom Assessment Cycle enables teachers to provide timely feedback and support to students based on the evidence collected. Feedback plays a crucial role in learners' reading participation, as it helps them understand their strengths, identify areas for growth, and make necessary adjustments. When teachers provide constructive feedback, learners are encouraged to reflect on their reading strategies, refine their comprehension skills, and actively participate in the reading process. Additionally, timely support ensures that students receive the necessary interventions or enrichment activities to enhance their reading participation. The analysis of assessment data is a key component of the Classroom Assessment Cycle that significantly influences learners' reading participation. By carefully analyzing assessment results, teachers gain valuable insights into students' reading strengths and weaknesses. This analysis guides instructional decision-making, allowing teachers to adapt and differentiate their reading instruction based on students' specific needs. By tailoring instruction to address individual learning gaps, teachers can increase learners' reading participation and foster a more inclusive and engaging reading environment. The final component of the Classroom Assessment Cycle involves modifying instruction based on the analysis of assessment data. By identifying areas where students may struggle or require additional support, teachers can adjust their instructional strategies, materials, and activities to promote active reading participation. Modifying instruction ensures that teaching methods align with students' needs and preferences, fostering a sense of relevance and engagement. By continuously adapting instruction to meet learners' evolving needs, teachers can create a dynamic reading environment that supports and enhances reading participation.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions.

The extent of classroom assessment cycle in terms of modifying instruction (3.66), learning targets (3.58), and gathering evidence (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while, analyzing assessment data (3.39) is sometimes manifested. The

overall mean rating of 3.53 denotes the extent of extent of classroom assessment cycle is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. The extent of comprehension of senior high school learners in terms of discussing with friend (3.15), listening to the lesson (3.14), being relevant to the teaching and learning activities (3.04) and writing (2.80) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes that extent of comprehension of senior high school learners is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between classroom assessment cycle ($r=0.857$; $p_i.000$) and learners' reading participation. Domains of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets (0.001), gathering evidence (0.002), analyzing assessment data (0.000) and modifying instruction (0.001) significantly influenced learners' reading participation.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The classroom assessment cycle in terms of modifying instruction, learning targets, gathering evidence and assessment data is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. The comprehension of senior high school learners in terms of discussing with friend, listening to the lesson, being relevant to the teaching and learning activities (and writing is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation. Domains of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets, gathering evidence analyzing assessment data and modifying instruction significantly influenced learners' reading participation.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. Encourage and support ongoing professional development for teachers on effective implementation of the Classroom As-

essment Cycle. Provide resources, workshops, and training sessions to enhance their understanding and skills in utilizing assessment data to inform instruction and improve learners' reading participation. Create opportunities for collaboration among teachers within the district to share best practices, strategies, and experiences related to the implementation of the Classroom Assessment Cycle. Foster a supportive environment where educators can learn from one another and collaborate to improve reading participation district-wide. Ensure that teachers have access to adequate resources, such as assessment tools, instructional materials, and technology, to effectively implement the Classroom Assessment Cycle. Support teachers in their efforts to gather evidence, analyze data, and modify instruction by providing them with the necessary tools and support systems. School Principal. Work collaboratively with teachers to develop a shared vision and understanding of the importance of the Classroom Assessment Cycle in enhancing learners' reading participation. Ensure that the implementation of the cycle aligns with the school's mission and goals. Provide instructional leadership by modeling effective assessment practices and supporting teachers in their implementation of the Classroom Assessment Cycle. Encourage and recognize teachers' efforts to integrate assessment practices that enhance reading participation. Encourage regular reflection and data analysis among teachers to identify areas for improvement in the implementation of the Classroom Assessment Cycle. Support teachers in developing action plans to address areas of concern and celebrate successes in improving reading participation.

Teacher. Take advantage of professional development opportunities offered by the district and school to deepen understanding and skills related to the Classroom Assessment Cycle. Stay updated with research and best practices in assessment and reading instruction. Engage in collaborative discussions with colleagues to

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